

THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER EDUCATION AND THEIR PROTECTION IN BANKING SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The prime objective of the study is to analyse financial literacy among consumers and also examine the impact of financial literacy on consumer protection.

Design/Research Methodology/approach: A random sample of 212 customers was chosen as the respondents for the study. A self-administered questionnaire was used for the collection of primary data and distributed to the random samples and has been tested with standard deviation and one sample t-test.

Findings: This study has found that most of the respondents are unaware of the grievance redressal system exists for banking customers.

Research Implications: Financial Institutions are regulated to provide better products and services rather than taking advantage of financially illiterate consumers. By giving clear and specific information to its customers and providing adequate mechanisms to resolve the disputes of customers, financial institutions can deliver fair and honest services and protect the consumer interest

Scope for future work / Research limitations: This contribution mainly focused to analyse the financial literacy among consumers and also examine the impact of financial literacy on consumer protection. but it has not studied any other variables that may have impact on consumer protection in banking sector. Further this contribution surveyed 212 respondents from a particular city, hence the result may or may not be applicable to the other cities or states in India.

Originality/value: A literature review found that there are various studies on financial literacy and its impact on consumer protection. The paper describes how Socio demographic factors of the respondents are related to the financial literacy and consumer protection.

Key Words: Consumer Protection, Consumer unawareness, financial illiteracy,

Paper type: Research paper

INTRODUCTION

Consumer protection is the activity of safeguarding the interests of consumers while purchasing goods and services. Consumers are exploited as a result of unfair trade and economic practises in the workplace. Consumers must be informed of their rights and duties, as well as market conditions, in order to protect themselves from such exploitation. Consumers, particularly in the banking sector, must be aware of all rules and procedures. Banks, such as Maharashtra Co-operative Banks, also deceive consumers to achieve their operating goals (Akshay Ramesh and Gokul, 2019). The quantity of fraudulent actions carried out in the name of banks has also been recorded on numerous occasions. Scheduled

commercial banks reported approximately 84545 fraud cases totaling Rs. 1.85 crore (The Economic Times, 2020). From July 2019 to March 2020, a total of 2,14,480 complaints were received, with SBI receiving the most (63, 259 complaints), HDFC receiving 18764 complaints, ICICI bank receiving 14,582 complaints, Panjab National Bank receiving 12,469 complaints, and Axis bank receiving 12,214 complaints (The Economic Times, 2020). In India's banking sector, it is desperately needed for consumer protection.

A country's modern economy requires participation from its whole population. Only 60 percent to 70 percent of the population in most developing nations participates in formal banking activity. In today's economy, having access to basic banking services is critical. Financial services are used by the world's population for everyday transactions and savings. Individuals' socioeconomic progress is aided by access to financial services. Individuals' purchasing power is increased by banks and banking services, which promotes inclusive growth.

Small financial institutions, Micro Financial Institutions (MFIs), Cooperative Societies, Business Correspondents/Banking Mitras, Business Facilitators, and other innovations in the banking sector, such as small financial institutions, Micro Financial Institutions (MFIs), Cooperative Societies, Business Correspondents/Banking Mitras, Business Facilitators, and others, all play a key role in financial inclusion and financial literacy activities. People in India need to be encouraged to participate in more formal financial activities, which the government can do through various tactics such as depositing subsidies, pension funds, and other monetary advantages directly into beneficiaries' bank accounts.

Customer exploitation by banks and other financial institutions has been more common in recent years. Customers are approached by banks with a variety of credit products and other financial services. Over-indebtedness of consumers stated as a result of an increase in risky lending practises. The financial crisis of 2008 was caused by over lending under the housing plan.

Markets do not function on their own (Rodrik, 2007). Institutions are required to control markets, compensate losers, and offer safety nets. Without regulating agencies, markets will be neither honest nor efficient. Effective consumer protection is necessary to promote financial stability. Consumer rights are being protected through national and international reforms. Consumers must be well-educated about products and services in order to make informed decisions. If there are any issues or if any transactions go awry, this is a consumer protection mechanism. Consumers must be able to use the resource mechanism in order to resolve their problems. "Protection of consumers from loss of investments, scams and deceit, biased treatment and inadequate information, inexperienced staff of financial services companies, and severe discrimination" is the basis for financial market regulation (George Benston, 1999).

A consumer is a person who employs or uses any type of service in exchange for money from a bank. Locker rental.

A person who engages or avails of any service for consideration is defined as a "consumer" under the statute. As a result, in banking transactions, a customer of a bank who has a bank account with the bank, or a person who hires a locker facility or obtains a bank guarantee from a bank, are all "consumers" who can file complaints under the Act for "deficiency in service" on the part of the bank, or for "restrictive trade practise" or "unfair trade practise" adopted by the bank, are all "consumers" who can file complaints under the Act.

NEED FOR CONSUMER PROTECTION

It is caused by a power, information, and resource mismatch between the consumer and the financial institution, which puts the consumer at a disadvantage. Individual retail consumers find it difficult or expensive to receive appropriate information about their financial purchases, and consumers find it difficult to assess the relevance of complicated financial goods even receiving all available information.

Financial institutions can provide fair and honest services while also protecting consumer interests by providing clear and explicit information to their consumers and offering proper means to settle customer disputes. In order to maintain market discipline in the financial industry, customers must be empowered with information, basic rights, and obligations. Rather than taking advantage of financially ignorant customers, financial institutions are regulated to deliver better products and services.

Financial institutions increase demand for good governance and promote corporate standards by setting solid and transparent criteria for the delivery of financial services and accountability. Consumers can grasp the risk return connected with financial products and services if they are made aware of them. They may also learn how to maximise their financial worth. Financial literacy preserves consumers' rights and encourages financial inclusion, as well as encouraging customers to use financial services and gaining their trust.

Financial literacy organisations provide knowledge, skills, and confidence to help people understand and analyse the information they receive, as well as assess the risks and rewards associated with financial goods and services. In India, the Reserve Bank of India plays a key role in maintaining a strong and effective oversight over all financial institutions, as well as issuing recommendations to ensure that the public receives transparent banking services. Banking and financial institutions must answer to the Reserve Bank of India, as well as customer service departments, customer education departments, customer protection departments, and the Banking Ombudsman, among others.

Table no. 1: Areas of major Consumer Protection concern by level of financial sector development

Particulars	High-Income Countries	Middle-Income Countries	Low-Income Countries
Remittances / Payments	NA	NA	A
Micro-Finance	NA	NA	A
Micro-Credit	NA	NA	A
Consumer Credit	A	A	A
Data Protection	A	A	A
Debit/Credit Cards	A	A	A
Life Insurance	A	A	NA
Private Pensions	A	A	NA
Investment Funds	A	A	NA
Securities	A	A	NA
Exotic Mortgages	A	NA	NA

Source: world bank (2010)

Low-income countries are concerned about remittances and non-bank payment systems, whereas high-income countries are concerned about investment money and exotic residential mortgages, according to the table above (Rutledge, S.L 2020).

India, as a low-income country, has a Reserve Bank of India (RBI), which investigates all banking concerns and defends consumer interests through its laws and regulations. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) plays a pivotal role in safeguarding and enhancing consumer protection. The RBI's main responsibilities in protecting consumer interests are as follows:

- a. Establishment of a Consumer Redress Cell to assist consumers in resolving their problems
- b. In 2006, the Consumer Education and Protection Department was established to promote consumer financial literacy.
- c. The Banking Norms and Standard Boards of India (BCSBI), an autonomous agency, was established to promote banks' adherence to self-imposed codes for committed customer services.
- d. In 1995, the Banking Ombudsman was established, bolstering the institutional structure for dispute resolution. It is a technique for resolving conflicts between a bank and its clients through an alternative dispute resolution process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer happiness, according to Amruth Raj (2013), is a leading indication of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty. The study employed the most commonly used customer satisfaction metrics of market perception. Customer services, according to the definition, is the providing of services to customers prior to, during, and after the purchase of products and services.

"Customer service is a sequence of operations meant to raise the degree of consumer satisfaction, making the customer believe that a particular product or service has met their expectations," according to Turban et al., (2002).

By analysing customer delight in urban customer banking, Sharma and Sharma (2014) discovered that customers were satisfied with loan facilities, bank environment, routine work procedures, location, and interest rates, but they were dissatisfied with loan formalities and bank promotion / awareness programmes.

Internet banking is playing a crucial role in the financial sector, according to Gupta (2014). Customers' attitudes toward internet banking and traditional banking were studied, and it was discovered that internet banking was easier and faster than traditional banking. The correctness and confidentiality of internet banking transactions must be carefully monitored and considered the most critical element to consider.

Financial literacy, according to Natalie Gallery (2010), focuses on basic money management techniques such as budgeting, saving, investing, and insurance. It is not necessary to think about macro-economic financial literacy skills that influence individual decision-making.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of the study are as follows

1. To study the level of awareness on the consumer protection rights
2. Problems faced by the customers while using the banking services products
3. Impact of consumer financial illiteracy on consumer protection/exploitation

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study, titled "Impact of financial literacy on consumer protection with reference to bank customers in Dakshina Kannada district," is an empirical study based on quantitative data gathered from respondents. To obtain scientific results and meet the study objectives, the following research methodologies are employed.

- a. Sample size:** The sample size is limited to 212 persons from Gulbarga who have a bank account. The respondents were chosen using simple random sampling.
- b. Source of data:** In this study, both primary and secondary data were employed. A self-administered questionnaire was used to obtain primary data from 212 persons in Gulbarga city. Secondary data is gathered through research papers, documents published in various journals, and websites.
- c. Statistical tools used for analysis:** The data was analysed using the mean, standard deviation, and one sample t-test.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS OF THE RESPONDENTS.

The examination of the respondents' socio-demographic variables is critical in understanding how socio-economic factors affect financial literacy and consumer protection. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in the table below.

The socio demographic characteristics of the respondents are depicted in the table (no. 2). Gender, marital status, age, educational qualification, place of residence, occupation, and monthly income are all factors included in the study. According to the study, the majority of respondents (54.72 percent) are female, while the remaining 45.28 percent are male. As far as civil status is concerned, the majority of respondents (66.98 percent) are single; 1.88 percent are single parents, and 31.14 percent are married. The bulk of respondents are under the age of 20, with 47.16 percent falling into that category, and 19.82 percent falling into the age groups of 21-30 and 31-40. Only 13.2 percent of the population is over the age of 40. According to the above data, 60 percent of the respondents are graduates, 20.95 percent are postgraduates, 13.34 percent have completed high school, and the remaining 5.71 percent have other qualifications. The table also shows that 83.02 percent of respondents live in urban areas, while 16.98 percent live in rural areas. In terms of the respondents' occupations, 18.1 percent of respondents work for private companies, 14.28% are self-employed or own a business, 0.95 percent are retired, and 66.67 percent have other employment. According to the monthly income of the respondents, 48.12 percent have a monthly income of less than \$10,000, 21.7 percent have a monthly income of more than \$30,000, 18.86 percent have a monthly income of 10001-20000, and the remaining 11.32 percent have a monthly income of 20001-30000.

Table No. 2: Socio Demographic factors of the Respondents

Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Female	116	54.72
Male	96	45.28
Civil Status		
Single	142	66.98
Married	66	31.14
Single parent	4	1.88
Age		
Less than 20	100	47.16
21-30	42	19.82
31-40	42	19.82
41 and Above	28	13.20
Education		
High school	28	13.34
Graduate	126	60
Post graduate	44	20.95
Other	12	5.71

Place of domicile		
Urban	176	83.02
Rural	36	16.98
Occupation		
Private	38	18.10
Self-employed/Business	30	14.28
Retired	2	0.95
Other	140	66.67
Monthly Income		
Below 10000	102	48.12
10001-20000	40	18.86
20001-30000	24	11.32
Above 30000	46	21.70

Source: Primary Data

Customers Banking Activities:

Banks accept deposits in the form of basic savings bank accounts, fixed deposits, current accounts, recurring deposits, and lending loans for various purposes. Customers visit banks for a variety of reasons, according to the research. According to the survey respondents, as shown in table (no.3), the majority of respondents (83.01 percent) created a savings bank deposit account. Fixed deposits, current accounts, and recurring deposits come next. Only 1.89 percent of respondents use bank lending services, according to the research. The majority of respondents have a savings account because it is a basic prerequisite for access to most government amenities and people have a habit of going to formal banking activities. According to the report, 32.13 percent of respondents used financial services in the previous 1-5 years, while 24.48 percent used banking services in the previous year. From the last 5 to 15 years, 43.39 percent of respondents have used financial services.

Table no. 3: Customers Banking Activities

Types of accounts the preferred by respondents			Status of usage of the bank services by the respondents		
Type of accounts	N	%	Status of usage	N	%
Savings	176	83.01	Less than one year	54	24.48
Current	12	5.67	1-5 years	66	32.13
Fixed deposits	16	7.54	5-10 years	50	23.58
Recurring deposits	4	1.89	10-15 years	20	9.43
Loan	4	1.89	More than 15 years	22	10.38

Source: Primary Data

Mobile banking, Net banking, and ATM services have been developed to make banking products more accessible and to reach clients with brick-and-mortar institutions. Customers' access to banking goods and services is also greatly influenced by customer-friendly branch banks. Customers visit bank branches only on rare occasions (table no.4), according to the survey. Customers use the ATM service on a regular basis. Only 40.57 percent of those polled utilise mobile banking. Only 32.08 percent of those polled utilise online banking. The most popular banking services, according to the report, were user-friendly and easily accessible

ATMs and mobile banking. Customers must be knowledgeable about internet banking. Customers avoid branch banking since it is a time-consuming process, and because the majority of respondents have savings accounts, frequent visits to a bank branch are not required.

Table no. 4: Frequency of using banking services every month

Particulars	Frequently		Occasionally		Rarely	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Branch banking	44	20.75	84	39.62	84	39.62
ATM	110	51.89	72	33.96	30	14.15
Mobile banking	86	40.57	38	17.92	88	41.51
Net banking	68	32.08	38	17.92	106	50.00

Source: Primary Data

Degree of Awareness of Consumer Rights:

The result of the level of awareness of consumer rights is shown in table no.5. For our research, we looked at six Customer Rights indicators to see if there was a substantial difference in customer knowledge. The customer right indicators are decoded as R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, and R6 in the table above. The markers R1 and R6 have a mean value less than 2 (test value) in the table above, indicating that customers are unaware of their rights, such as the right to choose and the right to be safe. Customers are fairly aware of their rights such as the right to be heard, the right to be informed, the right to seek redress, and the right to consumer education, as indicated by the indicators R2, R3, R4, and R5, which have mean values more than 2 (2.05, 2.05, 2.10, and 2.08, respectively). For each indicator, the significance value of a one-sample t-test is greater than 0.05. This demonstrates that there are no substantial differences in consumer rights awareness.

Table no. 5: Level of awareness on the consumer rights

Consumer Rights	N	Df	Mean	Std. D	Std. E	T	Sig. (2-tailed)
Right to Choose (R1)	212	211	1.99	1.073	.104	-.090	.928
Right to be heard (R2)	212	211	2.05	1.018	.099	.477	.634
Right to be Informed (R3)	212	211	2.07	1.044	.101	.651	.516
Right to seek redressal (R4)	212	211	2.10	1.059	.103	1.008	.316
Right to consumer education (R5)	212	211	2.08	1.052	.102	.831	.408
Right to be Safety (R6)	212	211	1.92	.987	.096	-.886	.378

Source: Primary Data

Table no. 6 shows the outcome of respondents' difficulties gaining access to financial services. Six variables were evaluated to analyse challenges faced by customers when using banking services, namely P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, and P8, as indicated in the above table. General Banking, Deposit and Withdrawal, Loans, ATM Services, Debit and Credit Cards, and Customer Services are some of the banking services available. For each statement, the mean value, standard deviation, and significant value of a single sample t-test at a 5% significance level are shown in the table above. The results suggest that customers occasionally experience problems while using banking services P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, and P6 with mean values of 2.34, 2.38, 2.95, 2.42, 2.51, and 2.42 (>test value 2). The overall significance value for the above indicators is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 at a 5% level of significance. Because the significant value of the indicator-wise one-sample t-test is also less than 0.05. It may be inferred that there is a considerable disparity in the difficulties customers confront while attempting to obtain financial services.

Table no. 6: Problems faced while using the banking services products

Problems Faced during	N	Df	Mean	Std. D	Std. E	T	Sig. (2-tailed)
General Banking (P1)	212	211	2.34	.893	.087	3.915	.000
Deposit and Withdrawal (P2)	212	211	2.38	.951	.092	4.087	.000
Loans (P3)	212	211	2.95	.844	.082	11.626	.000
ATM services (P4)	212	211	2.42	.975	.095	4.385	.000
Debit and Credit Cards (P5)	212	211	2.51	1.035	.101	5.067	.000
Customer Services (P6)	212	211	2.42	.935	.091	4.572	.000

Source: Primary Data

The outcome of the source of information about consumer exploitation/protection is shown in table no. 7. Consumers can obtain information on consumer protection and exploitation from a variety of media, including newspapers, periodical books, radio, television, websites, family and friends, and professional associations. The purpose of the study is to determine which sources of information have the greatest impact. The table no. shows that the major sources of information, such as magazines, books, radio, and professional associations, have a mean value greater than 2 (test value), indicating that these sources have little impact on consumer awareness, whereas newspaper, television, website, and family friends have a mean value less than 2. For each indicator, the significance value of the one sample t-test is less than 0.05. That is to say, diverse sources of information have a substantial impact on customer awareness.

Table no. 7 : Impact of Source of information on consumer awareness on consumer protection/exploitation

Source of Information	N	Df	Mean	Std. D	Std. E	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Newspaper	212	211	1.96	.985	.096	-5.621	.000
Magazine books	212	211	2.30	.948	.092	-2.152	.034
Radio	212	211	2.75	1.161	.113	2.258	.026
Television	212	211	1.97	.961	.093	-5.662	.000
Website	212	211	1.69	.844	.082	-9.902	.000
Family Friends	212	211	1.76	.857	.083	-8.841	.000
Professional Association	212	211	2.21	1.084	.105	-2.777	.006

Source: Primary Data

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

The study's main findings include the socio-demographic profile of the sample population, consumers' access to banking goods and services, their level of awareness of consumer rights, the challenges they confront, and the information sources that influence their level of awareness.

The bulk of the respondents are young, unmarried, and earn less than Rs. 10,000, according to the survey. Because the majority of the responders are teenagers, it is evident that they only use bank savings accounts. The most popular services used by clients are ATMs and online banking. It is obvious that promoting a cashless economy will be viable if greater knowledge of internet banking and mobile banking services is generated.

The study also discovered that the majority of customers are unaware of their rights as consumers, implying that increased consumer awareness and responsibility is essential.

CONCLUSION

The majority of respondents are unaware of their rights and are so exploited by banks. In the banking sector, financial literacy and consumer protection will improve financial stability and customer welfare. We can observe from this study that most individuals are aware of their basic consumer rights, but they are unaware of the banking ombudsman act. The RBI's attempts to defend consumer protection in the banking industry will only yield results if people are made aware of the grievance redressal system, however the majority of respondents in this study are unaware of the banking ombudsman act. As a result, the RBI as well as the Indian government's federal government should take some policy actions to benefit customers.

REFERENCES

Aggarwal & Gupta, (2014, October), Awareness of Financial literacy among college students, *Journal of Management and Technology*, 1-13

- Huston, S. J. (2010). Measuring financial literacy. *Journal of consumer affairs*, 44(2), 296-316
- Reserve bank of India (2016). Reserve bank of India: Press release. Retrieved from Reserve Bank of India websites: https://www.rbi.org.in/Scripts/BS_PressReleaseDisplay.aspx?prid=47383
- Reserve bank of India (2018). Reserve bank of India: Press release. Retrieved from Reserve Bank of India websites: https://www.rbi.org.in/Scripts/FS_PressRelease.aspx?prid=48899&fn=2745
- Reserve bank of India (2018). Reserve bank of India: Overview. Retrieved from Reserve Bank of India websites: https://www.rbi.org.in/scripts/FS_Overview.aspx?fn=2745
- Reserve bank of India (2018). Reserve bank of India: Speeches. Retrieved from Reserve Bank of India websites: https://www.rbi.org.in/scripts/FS_Speeches.aspx?Id=1040&fn=2745
- Rutledge, S. L. (2010). *Consumer protection and financial literacy: lessons from nine country studies*. The World Bank.